

Using of Fieldworks Language Explorer (FLEX) in the analysis of verbs on educational discourse in online media: A case study in a "full day school"

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Abstract

FieldWorks Language Explorer (FLEX) is an application that provides tools for dictionary development, morphological analysis, decomposition, and so on. Using of FLEX application can facilitate researchers in analyzing the discourse quickly and practically. This paper discusses the FLEX application method by giving examples of using the application in analyzing educational discourse on full day school in Indonesia. The discourse is found from several online media, such as: *rappler.com*, *kompas.com*, and *tempo.co*. This analysis is conducted to represent positive and negative verbs in the educational discourse on the topic of full-day school in Indonesia.

Keywords:

Fieldworks Language Explorer (FLEX); verbs; discourse; online media

1 INTRODUCTION

In this modern era, the development of computers as one of the results of information technology in a very significant change in human life. Its presence becomes necessary due to the benefits generated in its use is significant. The impact of these developments led to the using of computers maximally in life, including in the education. The use of media which computers are equipped with software or modern applications is very useful on education (Iskandar, Patak, & Rusli, 2009), especially in the part of linguistics.

In the linguistics, a scientific organization that is called SIL International (Summer Institute of Linguistics) has created an application that allows language researchers to learn, develop, analyze, and documented languages in the world. This application is known as FLEX (Fieldworks Language Explorer). FLEX is used as a very effective support tool in the preparation of a complete dictionary. Also, the use of FLEX is also beneficial in analyzing discourse, especially to see the syntactic unit fragments in each clause in a discourse.

Discourse can be presented in five forms or variations of description, narration, exposition, argumentation, and persuasion (Van Dijk, 1993). The object of study in this paper is a discourse description, and the theme of this paper is education about full-day school in Indonesia. Description is a form of discourse that describes things according to actual circumstances, so that the reader can see, hear, smell, and feel what is depicted in accordance with the image of the author (Blommaert & Bulcaen, 2000; Fairclough, 2001, 2013; Rogers, Malancharuvil-Berkes, Mosley, Hui, & Joseph, 2005; Weiss &

Wodak, 2003, 2007). This type of discourse aims to convey impressions about something, with the nature of its movements, or something else to the reader. There are verbs in the discourse. Verbs are all words that express acts or behavior (Crystal, 1988). For example, typing, quoting, feeling, showering, eating and others. The researcher analyzes the verbs in the discourses of the object. The verbs that is found will be categorized based on their meaning, which is positive, negative, or neutral.

From the description of the background, the core problem of this research is how to use fieldworks language exploration program (FLEX) in analyzing verbs in educational discourse in online media. The other concern of this research is how the verbs in the educational discourse about full-day school in Indonesia in online media by using FLEX are. Meanwhile, the purpose of this study is demonstrating the effectiveness of using FLEX in analyzing discourse and showing the results of the analysis of verbs in the educational discourse about full-day school in Indonesia on online media.

2 THEORETICAL FRAMEWORK

2.1 Fieldworks Language Explorer Program (FLEX)

Fieldworks Language Explorer (FLEX) is an application that provides tools for dictionary development, morphological analysis and decomposition (Butler & van Volkinburg, 2007). The using of FLEX applications can make it easy for language activists to learn, develop, analyze, and document languages in the world quickly and practically. FLEX is one of the applications created by SIL (Black & Simons, 2006). Generally, this application is designed to document the languages in detail, which is usually called the creation of a complete dictionary. The main target is languages in the world that are almost lost, the number of speakers is minimal.

2.2 Discourse

Discourse is the complete languages in the logical hierarchy, and it is the highest or greatest logical unit. This discourse is realized in the form of a complete essay (novel, series of the encyclopedia), paragraphs, sentences or words that carry a complete message. This definition seems narrow because it is linguistic (Fairclough, 2013). There is a difference between discourse analysis and text analysis. The difference is the discourse analysis focuses on structures naturally present in spoken language, as there are many in discourse such as conversations, interviews, comments, and utterances. While the text analysis focuses on the structure of the written language, as it appears on 'text' such as essays, bulletin boards, traffic signs, and in chapters (in books) (Bussmann, 2006; Crystal, 1988, 1994, 2011; Richards & Schmidt, 2013).

Writing or discourse generally contains two things, namely the content and manner of disclosure or presentation (Thorne, 1993). Both of them influence each other. Furthermore, Blommaert and Bulcaen (2000); Rogers et al. (2005); Weiss and Wodak (2007) explained that discourse could be presented in five forms or variations of description, narration, exposition, argumentation, and persuasion. Discourse description is a paper that can depict a story (Kuiken, 2008; Paige, Rasinski, & Magpuri- Lavell, 2012; Sikora,

Kuiken, & Miall, 2011). More extended understanding is explained by Brewer (1980) that the definition of description is a form of discourse that seeks to present a thing or object of speech that makes the object as if the readers see the object or as if it was in front of the eyes of the readers. More briefly, the meaning of description is to describe or describe (Chaplen, 1970).

2.3 Online Media

“On” means is in progress, and “line” means line, line, distance and short theme, “online” means the process of accessing information is going on through the internet media (Echols & Shadily, 2010). The meaning of Media Online that is associated with the notion of media in the context of people communication. The word of media is for people communication media in the field of people communication science has specific characteristics, such as publicity and periodicity. Online media is a general term for a form of media based on telecommunications and multimedia, in which there are portals, websites, radio-online, TV-online, online newspapers, and so on.

3 RESEARCH METHODS

3.1 Data and Data Sources

Data are all measurements or observations that have been recorded for a particular purpose (Mills & Gay, 2018; Neuman, 2014). The data in this study are three educational discourses that discuss about full-day school in Indonesia, first entitled Mendikbud: Full Day School policy is not canceled but strengthened, the second is entitled Jokowi: No Need to Worry about "Full Day School", and the third titled Minister Education: Five Day School Rules Is Up. Specifically, however, the sample data in this study focuses on the verbs in the three discourses.

The data source is the subject from which a data can be obtained where data obtained by using specific methods either in the form of humans, artifacts, or documents. The data in this research sourced from online media with the different website address. The first discourse obtained from *rappler.com*. The second obtained from *kompas.com* and the third obtained *tempo.co*.

3.2 Method of collecting data

The data collection method is a way used to obtain or collect data needed in research. The research method is a scientific way to get data with a specific purpose and usefulness (Crano & Brewer, 2005). The data in this study obtained by accessing social networking through search discourse on *google.com* by entering the keyword discourse of full-day school education in Indonesia. Furthermore, the researchers choose the emerging discourses by selecting the three best discourses related to the topic of discussion. The selected discourse is sourced from *rappler.com*, *kompas.com*, and *tempo.co*.

3.3 Methods Data analysis

Data analysis is the process of arranging the sequence of data, organizing it into a pattern, category, and set of basic descriptions (Blaxter, Hughes, & Tight, 2010; Bordens & Abbott, 2008; Cohen, Manion, & Morrison, 2007). In analyzing the data of this study used a tool called *flex8.1.0* which was introduced by Levinson. This data analysis tool is in the form of an application that has been arranged in such a way that it is very easy to detect the verbs in

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the three discourses. Also, using this application allows researchers to see the percentage of use of each of the same verbs.

4 RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

4.1 Use of Fieldworks Language Explorer Program (FLEX) In Verbs Analysis On Education Discourse in Online Media

In the FLEX program, there are many features or items with various special functions. The feature or item that serves to analyze a text or discourse, there are texts & words. Here are the steps to use FLEX in analyzing verbs in educational discourse in online media about full-day school in Indonesia.

4.1.1 Download and install the app

To be able to use FLEX, first the researchers download and install the application. The FLEX application can be downloaded on the SIL website by accessing the link www.sil.org.

4.1.2 Open texts & words

After downloading and installing the application, the next step done by the researchers is to open the application. However, in the application, many features or items have their function. Specifically for analyzing syntactic unit fragments in discourse, the items used are texts & words.

4.1.3 Incorporate and analyze discourse

After opening texts and words, researchers put the discourse on the "Baseline" column. After entering the discourse, to analyze in detail every word split (morphological analysis) can be used "Analyze" column. However, because this study focuses only on the use of verbs, the researchers used text column only. In this column text chart researchers easily detect one by one verb in the discourse.

4.1.4 Clicking on the word analysis column

To see the percentage of use of each word in a previously analyzed discourse on a "text chart" column, the researcher clicks on a column of word "analyses." In a very short time, the results of his percentage appear in detail.

4.1.5 Exporting data to Microsoft word

After analyzing and viewing the results of the analysis, researchers exported the results of such analysis into Microsoft word. It is done to facilitate researchers to pour it into writing. Also, by exporting the results of such analysis into Microsoft word, researchers can edit the results of the analysis again that sort results according to the focus of research. This research focuses on verbs, so the authors only take the results of the analysis of the use of verbs and remove the results of analysis of other syntactic units.

4.2 Verbs in the Education Discourse on Full Day School in Indonesia on Online Media

In this research, the researcher analyzes three discourses of education about full-day school in Indonesia on online media by using FLEX. Three discourses have a different title that source sites, namely: first titled Mendikbud: full day school policy is not canceled but reinforced, sourced from rappler.com, herein after referred to as Data 1. Second, the discourse is entitled Jokowi: no need to

worry about "full day school," obtained from *kompas.com*, herein after referred to as Data 2. Third, a discourse entitled Minister of Education: five-day school rules have been issued, taken from *tempo.co*, which is referred to as Data 3. After analyzing these three data using FLE_x, the following results are found:

4.2.1 Data 1

The total number of words in the data 1 of 436 words including repeated words and the number of words used as many as 375 (not including repeated words). Of the total words used there are 33 verbs (verbs).

Table 1. Verbs in data 1

Verbs of Data 1		Verbs of Data 1	
Indonesian	English	Indonesian	English
membantah	argue	merealisasikan	realize
dibatalkan	to be canceled	ditemui	to be found
diperkuat	to be strengthened	dicabut	to be revoked
menjadi	to be	berjalan	walk
ditata ulang	to be rearranged	dilakukan	to be done
ujar	speak	merupakan	comprise
mengatakan	say	menyiapkan	prepare
menunggu	waiting	adalah	is
melibatkan	involve	mendapat	got
melihat	look	disampaikan	to be delivered
berharap	hope	menepis	brush aside
mengatur	Yes	menyebut	mention
menghadirkan	present	dikaji	to be studied
menegaskan	talk about	dijalankan	to be run
merasa	feel	mengakui	admit
mengklarifikasi	clarify	menyesuaikan	adjust
muncul	appear		

Based on the 33 verbs in Table 1 above, the verbs are classified as eleven positive verbs, five negative verbs, and seventeen neutral verbs. The following Table 2 provides information on verb classification based on the Table 1 above.

Table 1. Verbs classification of data 1

Verbs					
Positive		Negative		Neutral	
Indonesian	English	Indonesian	English	Indonesian	English
diperkuat	strengthen	membantah	argue	menjadi	to be
ditata ulang	rearranged	dibatalkan	canceled	ujar	speak
berharap	hope	melibatkan	involve	mengatakan	say
mengatur	set	dicabut	revoked	menunggu	wait
menghadirkan	present	menepis	brush aside	merasa	feel
menegaskan	confirms			ditemui	found
mengklarifikasi	clarify			berjalan	walk
merealisasikan	realize			dilakukan	done
menyiapkan	prepare			adalah	is
mengakui	to admit			mendapat	got
menyesuaikan	adjust			disampaikan	delivered
				menyebut	mention
				dikaji	studied
				dijalankan	

4.2.2 Data 2

The total number of words in data 2 as many as 351 words including repeated words and the number of words used as much as 293 (not including repeated words). Of the total words used there are 25 verbs (verbs). Table 3 below provides verbs in data 2.

Table 3. Verbs in data 2

Verbs of Data 2		Verbs of Data 2	
Indonesian	English	Indonesian	English
meminta	ask	menggantikan	replace
disampaikan	to be delivered	mendapatkan	get
mengunggah	upload	mematikan	turn off
diberi	to be given	menjadi	to be
mengatakan	say	mencapai	reach
menerapkan	apply	menegaskan	confirms
melanjutkan	continue	menolak	reject
dipertahankan	to be maintained	mencabut	revoke
disetujui	to be approved	ditemui	to be found
mulai	start	menyebut	mention
menutup	close	menjalankan	run
menyampaikan	deliver	memperlihatkan	replace
menerbitkan	publish		

Based on the 25 verbs in Table 3 above, the verbs in data 2 are classified as 10 positive verbs, 5 negative verbs, and 10 neutral verbs. The details of the classification is presented in Table 4 below.

Table 4. Verbs classification of data 2

Verbs					
Positive		Negative		Neutral	
Indonesian	English	Indonesian	English	Indonesian	English
menerapkan	apply	menggantikan	replace	meminta	ask
melanjutkan	continue	mematikan	turn off	disampaikan	to be delivered
dipertahankan	to be maintained	menolak	reject	mengunggah	upload
disetujui	to be proved	mencabut	revoke	diberi	to be given
menerbitkan	publish	menutup	close	mengatakan	say
mendapatkan	get			mulai	start
mencapai	reach			menyampaikan	deliver
menegaskan	confirms			menyebut	mention
menjalankan	run			ditemui	to be found
Memperlihatkan	show			menjadi	to be

4.2.3 Data 3

The total number of words in data 3 are 323 words in which including repeated words and the number of words used as many as 262 (not including repeated words). Of the total words used there are 22 verbs (verbs). The following Table 5 provides information of verbs in data 3.

Table 5. Verbs in data 3

Verb Data 3		Verb Data 3	
Indonesian	English	Indonesian	English
menyatakan	state	menilai	rate
menerbitkan	publish	mengganggu	disturb
berlaku	apply	dilakukan	was done
merupakan	is a	belajar	learn
masuk kerja	come to work	melengkapi	complete
menjelaskan	explain	menguatkan	strengthen
menyamakan	equalize	meminta	ask
diukur	be measured	mengkaji	review
mengajar	teach	membuat	make
tatap muka	face to face	menempuh	go through
istirahat	break	gulung tikar	out of business

Based on the 22 verbs in Table 5 above, the verbs in the data 3 above are classified as 8 positive verbs, 2 negative verbs, and 12 neutral verbs. Thus, Table 6 below provides the classification of verbs based on the Table 5.

Table 6. Verbs classification of data 3

Verbs					
Positive		Negative		Neutral	
Indonesian	English	Indonesian	English	Indonesian	English
menerbitkan masuk kerja	publish come to work	mengganggu gulung tikar	disturb out of business	menyatakan berlaku	stated apply
mengajar belajar melengkapi menguatkan	teach learn complete strengthen			merupakan menjelaskan menyamakan diukur	is a explain equalize to be measured
mengkaji	review			tatap muka	face to face
menempuh	go through			istirahat menilai dilakukan meminta membuat	break rate do ask make

5 CONCLUSION

Based on the results of the research can be concluded that the use of FLEx in analyzing the discourse is very useful. Analysing the fragment of syntactic units, items used texts and words, word analyses, and text charts. Next, to export the file to Microsoft Word, there are export items in the file field. For the results of the analysis can also be concluded that neutral verbs dominate the verbs in the three discourses, then positive verbs. Moreover, negative verbs are very few. This shows that in the writing of educational discourse neutral and positive verbs are used widely.

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